

Ultrasonic velocity and allied parameters of 1,1'-bis-*p*(*m/p*-methylbenzoyloxyphenyl)cyclohexane in tetrahydrofuran at 30°

K. M. Rajkotia and P. H. Parsania*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005, India

Manuscript received 30 July 1997, revised 28 April 1998, accepted 17 July 1998

Limiting apparent molar volume, compressibility, viscosity *A* and *B* coefficients of 1,1'-bis-*p*(*m/p*-methylbenzoyloxyphenyl)cyclohexane in THF at 30° have been evaluated from measurement of sound velocity, density and viscosity of these isomers in THF. The results have been interpreted in the light of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions.

The structures, nature and prevailing conditions of solvents and solutes play an important role on resulting properties and interactions occurring in the solutions¹. With this consideration, the present work reports ultrasonic velocity and allied parameters of *m*- and *p*-methyl-substituted esters (1 and 2) in THF at 30°.

Results and Discussion

The variation of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of esters 1 and 2 with different concentrations (C) are reported in Table 1. In order to understand the effect of methyl substitution on solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in THF solutions, various parameters such as apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k), isentropic compressibility (K_s) and solvation number (S_n) were calculated using standard equations² and are correlated with concentration.

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η), sound velocity (U), viscous relaxation strength (τ) and solvation number (S_n) for 1 and 2

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	$\rho \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg m ⁻³	η Pas	U m s ⁻¹	$\tau \cdot 10^{13}$ s	S_n
Ester 1					
0.0000 ^a	0.9499	0.4955	1263.0	4.36	—
0.0099	0.9512	0.5089	1267.5	4.44	0.65
0.0198	0.9521	0.5178	1270.5	4.49	0.82
0.0297	0.9529	0.5309	1277.4	4.55	0.70
0.0396	0.9540	0.5453	1278.0	4.67	1.09
0.0495	0.9560	0.5577	1282.2	4.73	0.91
0.0595	0.9559	0.5655	1287.6	4.76	0.92
Ester 2					
0.0000	0.9499	0.4955	1263.0	4.36	—
0.0099	0.9510	0.5167	1265.1	4.52	0.61
0.0198	0.9517	0.5302	1267.5	4.62	0.77
0.0297	0.9525	0.5455	1269.6	4.74	0.95
0.0396	0.9532	0.5596	1272.0	4.84	1.08
0.0495	0.9541	0.5803	1274.4	4.99	1.16
0.0595	0.9552	0.5947	1277.4	5.09	1.20

Jones-Dole³ constants *A* and *B* were determined from the intercept and slope of $(\eta_r - 1)\sqrt{C}$ against \sqrt{C} plots respectively (Table 2). The ϕ_v and ϕ_k values of both the samples were determined from the intercepts of ϕ_v and ϕ_k against \sqrt{C} plots respectively, and solute-solute interaction parameters (S_v and S_k) from their slopes (Table 2). The plots are linear over the concentration range 0.02–0.06 mol dm⁻³. From Table 2, it is clear that the values of *A* and *B* for ester 2 are greater than that of ester 1. The positive values of *A* and *B* indicate strong solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions. Solute-solute interaction for ester 1 is approximately three times larger than that of ester 2. The apparent molar volume is influenced by several factors, such as solvation phenomena, nature of the solute, etc. to different extent. The negative values of ϕ_k^0 and positive values of S_k indicate respectively strong electrostrictive solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions with increasing concentration. The electrostriction makes the solvent molecules considerably less compressible than bulk solvent due to the formation of rigid structure of solvent molecules around the solute molecules which increase the apparent molar volume. The positive values of S_n (Table 1) indicates solvating tendency of both the isomers and ester 2 has more solvating tendency compared to ester 1. This can be explained in terms of interaction between ester group and THF. The more electropositivity of ester 2 results in strong solute-solvent interaction compared to ester 1 and hence more change in apparent molar volume of ester 2. Ester 2 forms linear structure with solvent molecules which is more compressible compared to non-linear structure formed by ester 1. Thus, solvophobicity is due to electrostatic repulsion between lone-pairs of solvent and solute molecules, whereas solvophilicity is due to electrostatic attraction between lone-pair of solvent and electropositive solute which results in the formation of rigid structure of solvent molecule around the solute molecules.

The solvation of solute molecules causes change in limiting apparent molar volume and apparent molar compressibility of the solute. In the present case, change in ϕ_v and ϕ_k values of ester 2 are more compared to ester 1 be-

cause of more electropositive nature of ester 2 which is further supported by viscosity *B* coefficient of ester 2.

Table 2. Jones-Dole constants (*A* and *B*), limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) and limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k^0) and solute-solute interaction parameters (S_v and S_k) for esters 1 and 2

Ester	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	$\phi_v^0 \cdot 10^6$ m ³	$S_v \cdot 10^6$	$\phi_k^0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ TPa ⁻¹	$S_k \cdot 10^{-4}$
1	0.0159	2.38	405.3	86.2	-18.281	5.692
2	0.1204	2.81	433.4	31.3	-1.987	2.066

The contribution of acoustic relaxation is attributed to entropic fluctuation associated with dynamically formed physical structure. The viscous relaxation strength (τ) (Table 1) increases with concentration and it is somewhat more for ester 2 compared to ester 1 because of more change in molecular volume of ester 2 due to solvation. In conclusion, ester 2 has more solvating tendency compared to ester 1 because of more electropositive nature of the former.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran was purified by fractional distillation. Esters 1 and 2 were synthesized from 1,1'-bis(4-hydro-

xyphenyl)cyclohexane and *m/p*-methylbenzoyl chlorides, and repeatedly crystallized from methanol-water system prior to use⁴. The ester solutions of different molarities were prepared in THF.

The density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of THF and each solution were measured at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using a specific gravity bottle, a suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer and a single crystal multifrequency interferometer (M-82) operating at 3 MHz with accuracies of ± 0.0001 g cm⁻³, $\pm 0.1\%$ and $\pm 0.05\%$ respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. R. Parikh for facilities and encouragement.

References

1. G. K. Johri and R. C. Misra, *Acustica*, 1985, **57**, 292; A. V. Rao, G. K. Raman and A. V. Rajulu, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1993, **5**, 582; K. Ch. Rao, A. V. Rajulu and S. V. Naidu, *Acta Polym.*, 1989, **40**, 743; H. Eyring and J. F. Kincaid, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1932, **61**, 620; M. Woldan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, **269**, 628.
2. A. R. Shah and P. H. Parsania, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1997, **14**, 33.
3. G. Jones and M. Dole, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
4. K. M. Rajkotia and P. H. Parsania, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 524.